

SHELTER MAPPING USING AI & SATELLITE IMAGERY

Sept 2022

AUTHOR(S):

Manith Adikari

SUPERVISOR(S):

Edoardo Nemni

Sofia Vallecorsa

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisors Edoardo Nemni and Sofia Vallecorsa who helped in making this project a success.

Also, I would like to acknowledge Kristina Gunne for all her efforts in organizing the CERN Openlab 2022 summer student program.

Finally, I would like to give a special thanks to everyone else at Openlab and the wider community of CERN who made this summer an invaluable experience.

ABSTRACT

Delivering humanitarian aid is critical in handling crises such as natural disasters and man-made conflicts. However, during these scenarios, it can be difficult to gather any information that could be valuable for an effective humanitarian response. Therefore, a possible solution is to use satellite imagery and analyze this data to infer information.

A popular satellite image analysis task is 'Shelter Mapping' which involves counting the number of settlements within an area such as a town. This would provide useful information such as the approximate human population affected by a disaster. This work is being conducted by UNOSAT (United Nations Satellite Centre) which is the key stakeholder in this project. However, in current shelter mapping, a difficulty is that the entire process is done manually by humans which can be time-consuming and laborious. The focus of this project was to address this problem by developing a pipeline to automate shelter mapping using machine learning. This would enable analysts at UNOSAT to accelerate the current shelter mapping process and more effectively deliver humanitarian aid.

A machine learning-based pipeline automating shelter mapping was successfully developed. Using this system, a Mask RCNN (Mask Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network) was successfully trained, with losses converging appropriately, using 13 satellite image datasets (these were manually labeled beforehand with all the shelters). The pipeline involves firstly preparing the labeled datasets by tiling (splitting the larger satellite image into smaller tiles) and converting to COCO format (common in machine learning object detection tasks). Afterward, the satellite image tiles and COCO data were used to train a machine learning model, in this case, a Mask RCNN. Further work is necessary before practical deployment by UNOSAT, including hyperparameter tuning, implementing regularisation techniques, and experimenting with other machine learning architectures.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	1
ABSTRACT	2
1 INTRODUCTION	4
2 PROJECT AIMS & STAKEHOLDERS	6
3 METHODOLOGY	6
3.1 DATASETS & PREPARATION	6
3.2 TRAINING & TESTING THE MODEL	8
4 IMPLEMENTATION	9
4.1 Dataset Preparation	9
4.2 Model Training	9
5 RESULTS & FUTURE WORK	10
6 CONCLUSION	11
7 REFERENCES	11

1 INTRODUCTION

Humanitarian relief is an essential response to mitigate the effects of natural and man-made disasters. To deliver an effective response, it is important to collect detailed information about the crisis, such as the number of people affected. However, in such situations, gathering information could be challenging for a multitude of reasons: poor access to the location, damaged infrastructure, and man-made conflict preventing access.

Using remote-sensing data is a promising way to address this issue. A common source of data is satellites, which can gather high-resolution imagery of the area of interest within a few days. Depending on the crisis, numerous analysis tasks are conducted using satellite image data, such as estimating the population of a settlement. UNOSAT (United Nations Satellite Centre), one of the key stakeholders of this project, carries out such tasks following humanitarian emergencies. Further information about UNOSAT is given in Section 2.

Figure 1: Satellite image of a settlement with numerous shelters which need to be identified during analysis

Currently, however, satellite image analysis requires human analysts which can be time-consuming and arduous, as evident in Figure 1. Therefore, automating these procedures would be beneficial in delivering more effective humanitarian responses. A promising method is to implement machine learning (ML) based algorithms, given the successes and advancements within this field.

For some time now, machine learning methods have been implemented in analyzing remote-sensing data. Numerous reviews have already been written looking at using neural networks, decision trees, random forests, support vector machines, and k-nearest neighbors [1, 6, 7, 9]. In current image analysis, deep learning methods are particularly popular [10, 11, 12]. Deep learning techniques have allowed increased 'end-to-end learning' where the model learns feature representations while tuning relevant parameters. This is a key improvement compared to previous analysis methods which involved several stages, such as manual feature selection, model training, and post-processing [10]. Notable deep-learning methods currently used in remote sensing are auto-encoders, which can classify different objects in an image by mapping image pixels to new values.

However, some of the drawbacks of deep learning are the requirements for large datasets and

computational power. For these reasons, in satellite-image analysis, it is often impractical to train models from scratch for new problems. Hence, it is common to take a pre-trained model and use transfer learning to solve the new problem. Additionally, the application of machine learning methods is limited by the satellite image resolution and the uniformity/calibration of sensors. For instance, higher-resolution image data could enable more elaborate analysis, but it is essential to consider the changes over time across locations.

Figure 2: Shelters mapped on a satellite image using an machine learning based approach

Shelter mapping is a common satellite-image analysis task, which entails counting the number of different structures within a particular region, such as a refugee settlement. As seen by Figure 2, having human analysts do this work can be inefficient compared to using an automated system. This task can be framed as an object detection problem solvable using ML, which will be the main focus of this project. A detailed review of shelter mapping has been done in [10].

Object detection usually involves outputting a bounding box (the limits of each object) for all relevant objects within an image (Figure 2). Region-proposal convolutional neural networks (RCNNs) are a popular object detection technique used within this field.

Shelter mapping as an object detection problem is difficult for the following reasons: variation in shelters/settlements, the objects' small sizes/clusters, and the requirement for high accuracy. At UNOSAT, there is ongoing research ([2, 5, 8]) to tackle these issues and efforts to implement them for practical use. This project will be an extension of the work conducted by UNOSAT in shelter mapping. This work could contribute to improving humanitarian responses, by enabling UNOSAT and relevant parties to gather critical information more effectively.

The remaining sections of the report include the following: project aims, methodology, implementation, results & future work, and conclusion.

2 PROJECT AIMS & STAKEHOLDERS

The overall aim of this project is to develop a satellite image analysis pipeline that automates shelter mapping using machine learning. This would mainly be used by the primary stakeholders, UNOSAT analysts, in practical deployment for real-world shelter mapping. This work would contribute to delivering more effective humanitarian responses.

The primary stakeholder for this project is UNOSAT (United Nations Satellite Centre) which uses remote-sensing satellite data to deliver humanitarian aid. This project is also done in collaboration with CERN Openlab which has organized the Summer Student Programme and provided numerous resources required to deliver the project.

Previous work conducted by UNOSAT/CERN includes the "Shelter-AI Building Footprint" repository which served as the basis for this project. However, note that this past version was not practically deployed nor demonstrated to work. Therefore, the current project will entail making fixes, improvements, and extensions. The successful completion of this project will involve deploying an initial functioning pipeline that could execute shelter mapping for most expected cases. With further work, the system should be ready for practical deployment by UNOSAT.

3 METHODOLOGY

The Project methodology could be divided into the following stages:

3.1 DATASETS & PREPARATION

Firstly, this stage will entail gathering the input satellite image datasets (images given in .TIF format and .shp shape files) which were manually annotated by UNOSAT. The annotations include all the locations of the shelters within each image. The datasets used are given in Table 1.

Satellite Image Training Datasets		
Country Name	ISO ALPHA 3 Code	Site
Chad	TCD	Malmarie
Kenya	KEN	Dagahaley
Nigeria	NGA	Federal Training Center
Nigeria	NGA	Guibo
Nigeria	NGA	Maissandari Stadium
Nigeria	NGA	Maissandari Teachers Ville
South Sudan	SSD	JamJang
Syria	SYR	Al Hol
Syria	SYR	Abu Khashab
Syria	SYR	Areeshah
Syria	SYR	Menbij
Syria	SYR	Mahmoudli
Tanzania	TZA	Nyarugusu

Table 1: List of Satellite Image Datasets used for training.

Figure 3: An image tile processed from a larger satellite image

Figure 4: A visualization of an image tile once converted to COCO format

Afterwards, these image files will be tiled (an example is shown in Figure 3) and converted to COCO dataset format (an example is shown in Figure 4). COCO is a commonly used dataset format for object detection and is chosen for this project given its widespread use. The output of this dataset preparation stage will be image tiles (forming each of the satellite images) with COCO data files.

This stage will involve developing a Python script capable of executing these processes (tiling and conversion to COCO). An important aspect will be to have appropriate file management, which is crucial for practical deployment.

3.2 TRAINING & TESTING THE MODEL

A Mask Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (Mask RCNN) (as shown in Figure 5) will be trained using the datasets prepared from the previous stage. This architecture was selected given its successes in object detection [4] as well as previous work by UNOSAT. Depending on initial training results, modifications to the network (E.g. learning rate) will be made and other architectures may be considered.

Figure 5: Architecture of a Mask Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (Mask RCNN)

Afterward, test the model with unseen satellite image data and visualise how successful the shelter mapping is (this will be shown by plotting the bounding boxes on the input image as seen in 6). Further work could involve trying new model architectures and hyperparameter tuning.

Figure 6: Example of an image tile after shelter mapping

4 IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the aforementioned methodology is detailed below.

4.1 Dataset Preparation

The work was conducted primarily on ml.cern.ch which is a centralized service capable of running machine learning workloads. The dataset preparation code was executed on a Ubuntu notebook created on this service using a docker file and with EOS as storage for all the datasets.

The previous work in the "Shelter-AI Building Footprint" repository contained Python scripts and a docker file to prepare the image datasets. However, a significant amount of the dataset preparation code had to be modified due to poor functionality. The dataset preparation consists of tiling the input satellite images and constructing the COCO datasets, as well as splitting these files (for model training and testing).

The existing docker file for installing packages had numerous issues (e.g. version incompatibilities) therefore a new docker file was developed to install the following packages on the notebook: Pytorch, pycocotools, MMCV, GDAL, pillow, scikit-image. It took a significant amount of time to identify the appropriate package versions and ensure compatibility. Furthermore, it was essential to verify the correct prerequisites were installed on the workspace (E.g. Microsoft Build Tools C++, GCC Compiler). A particular difficulty was ensuring the CUDA version was compatible with the latest Ubuntu versions. Many of these issues were resolved by simply debugging the code or implementing specific solutions suggested by other open-source developers.

In addition to fixing issues, several new features were added to the dataset preparation Python code. Firstly, the file management was improved by ensuring there was a specified file/folder naming convention for the output. A detailed breakdown of the file management is given in the repository 'README'. Also, the user is now able to input the image source (e.g. WV2), countryISO3 (e.g. SSD), and the image clip size (e.g. 50 pixels) for each satellite image dataset before running the preparation script. In this case, the input datasets and output files were saved within the CERN EOS storage. This will be shown in the output image tiles and their file names. The output files for each dataset were set to be organised into the following folders: image tiles, training images, testing images, COCO format files.

Additional documentation was added to the repository and codebase which gives further information about running the dataset preparation.

4.2 Model Training

Using the prepared data (COCO data and image tiles stored on EOS) a Mask Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (Mask-RCNN) was trained remotely with a Nvidia T4 GPU for 40 Epochs with cross-entropy loss. The pre-trained network was obtained from the open-source MMDetection library [3].

Most of the code was based on the previous work (using PyTorch) but modifications had to be made to resolve incompatibilities issues and other library errors. Additionally, the training had to be conducted on a remote Linux distribution (due to requirements by packages). The

training was completed in over 4 hours for which the losses are plotted.

5 RESULTS & FUTURE WORK

Figure 7: Overview of current pipeline showing the stages: dataset preparation and model training

An overview of the current pipeline is illustrated in Figure 7. Dataset preparation was executed successfully using the datasets shown in Table 1. The inputs from each dataset were a shape file (.shp) with a mask .TIF image file. The outputs were image tiles, COCO format, and the data split for training and testing. The output files are organized in a folder with the corresponding dataset name with the chosen file naming convention. Within each of these folders are the image tiles and COCO files split into training and testing (with a split of 80-to-20 respectively).

Once the datasets for training and testing were prepared with the datasets, the Mask-RCNN model was trained remotely on a Nvidia T40 GPU as mentioned in the methodology section. The losses are plotted in Figure 8 which is converging though noisy. Given more time, applying regularisation techniques would have been sufficient to resolve this.

Future work should include implementing regularisation techniques to smoothen the losses and hyperparameter tuning. Additionally, experimenting with different models and datasets could be valuable. This would entail implementing an ML Ops process for the data preparation and training stages. If more time was available, thorough testing should be conducted to

Figure 8: Graph of losses after training Mask RCNN model

evaluate the shelter mapping models developed using this pipeline. Once this work is completed, the pipeline should be ready for practical deployment by UNOSAT analysts.

6 CONCLUSION

Gathering information is essential to delivering humanitarian aid but this can be difficult for reasons such as man-made conflict and poor accessibility to the affected area. A solution is to collect satellite imagery and analyze it for valuable information. An important task that could be executed is shelter mapping which is a common analysis task, involving counting the number of different structures within an area. However, this task could be time-consuming and arduous if manually done. The main objective of this project was to improve this process by developing an automated shelter mapping pipeline with machine learning. The key stakeholder is UNOSAT which intends to automate shelter mapping and practically deploy this pipeline.

A machine learning-based pipeline was developed which could prepare the required satellite image datasets by tiling the large satellite image and converting it to the appropriate COCO format with appropriate file management. These prepared datasets would then be used to train a neural network. Using this pipeline, a Mask RCNN was trained using 13 satellite image datasets on a Nvidia T40 GPU. The training was successful as evidenced by the converging losses but future work will be necessary before practical deployment by UNOSAT analysts. Further work could include implementing regularisation techniques, hyperparameter tuning, and trying out different architectures.

7 REFERENCES

- [1] Mariana Belgiu and Lucian Drăguț. “Random forest in remote sensing: A review of applications and future directions”. In: *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*

- 114 (Apr. 2016), pp. 24–31. DOI: [10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2016.01.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2016.01.011). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2016.01.011>.
- [2] Hongruixuan Chen et al. *Dual-Tasks Siamese Transformer Framework for Building Damage Assessment*. 2022. DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.2201.10953](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2201.10953). URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.10953>.
- [3] Kai Chen et al. *MMDetection: Open MMLab Detection Toolbox and Benchmark*. 2019. DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.1906.07155](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1906.07155). URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1906.07155>.
- [4] Kaiming He et al. “Mask R-CNN”. In: *2017 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*. 2017, pp. 2980–2988. DOI: [10.1109/ICCV.2017.322](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV.2017.322).
- [5] Tomaz Logar et al. “PulseSatellite: A tool using human-AI feedback loops for satellite image analysis in humanitarian contexts”. In: (2020). DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.2001.10685](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2001.10685). URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2001.10685>.
- [6] Aaron E. Maxwell, Timothy A. Warner, and Fang Fang. “Implementation of machine-learning classification in remote sensing: an applied review”. In: *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 39.9 (Feb. 2018), pp. 2784–2817. DOI: [10.1080/01431161.2018.1433343](https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2018.1433343). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2018.1433343>.
- [7] Giorgos Mountrakis, Jungho Im, and Caesar Ogole. “Support vector machines in remote sensing: A review”. In: *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 66.3 (May 2011), pp. 247–259. DOI: [10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2010.11.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2010.11.001). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2010.11.001>.
- [8] Edoardo Nemni et al. “Fully Convolutional Neural Network for Rapid Flood Segmentation in Synthetic Aperture Radar Imagery”. In: *Remote Sensing* 12.16 (Aug. 2020), p. 2532. DOI: [10.3390/rs12162532](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12162532). URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12162532>.
- [9] Elodie Pagot and Martino Pesaresi. “Systematic Study of the Urban Postconflict Change Classification Performance Using Spectral and Structural Features in a Support Vector Machine”. In: *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing* 1.2 (June 2008), pp. 120–128. DOI: [10.1109/jstars.2008.2001154](https://doi.org/10.1109/jstars.2008.2001154). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1109/jstars.2008.2001154>.
- [10] John A. Quinn et al. “Humanitarian applications of machine learning with remote-sensing data: review and case study in refugee settlement mapping”. In: *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* 376.2128 (Aug. 2018), p. 20170363. DOI: [10.1098/rsta.2017.0363](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2017.0363). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2017.0363>.
- [11] Liangpei Zhang, Lefei Zhang, and Bo Du. “Deep Learning for Remote Sensing Data: A Technical Tutorial on the State of the Art”. In: *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine* 4.2 (2016), pp. 22–40. DOI: [10.1109/MGRS.2016.2540798](https://doi.org/10.1109/MGRS.2016.2540798).
- [12] Xiao Xiang Zhu et al. “Deep Learning in Remote Sensing: A Comprehensive Review and List of Resources”. In: *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine* 5.4 (2017), pp. 8–36. DOI: [10.1109/MGRS.2017.2762307](https://doi.org/10.1109/MGRS.2017.2762307).

†

